

Towards Near-zero Energy Buildings: Lessons Learnt from the RE-cognition project

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Abstract:

The building sector is accountable for the 40% of the energy consumed and 36% of carbon emissions in the EU. At the same time, ambitious energy targets are required for a substantial reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in the forthcoming years. To tackle this challenge, a possible approach consists in boosting the adoption of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) at the places where energy is consumed (decentralized approach), minimizing carbon emissions. Hence, the path towards near-zero Energy Buildings (nZEBs) is regarded as one of the most viable solutions to meet the de-carbonization goal. However, a certain technological and policy-driven push is required for improving the actual inefficient European building stock. In this context, the RE-cognition project proposes an ICT (information and communications technologies) integration framework on top of established and ad-hoc designed renewable energy technologies. This paper presents how such an integration framework can be applied to a real building. The case study is a facility located in Turin, Italy, known as Energy Center, where companies, public administration and university researchers are hosted. Here, the existing photovoltaic system (PV), ground-source heat pump (GSHP) and district heating substation (DH) are coupled with a newly developed Latent Heat Thermal Storage (LHTS) and an innovative micro turbine for the cogeneration of heat and power (m-CHP). Results discuss the insights gained in advancing this pilot site towards an effective near-zero Energy Building.

Keywords:

Near-zero Energy Building, RES integration, multi-energy system, EU project, pilot site

Conference topic:

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1. Introduction

It is estimated that the building sector is accountable for 40% of the primary energy consumption and 36% of carbon emissions in Europe [1]. On the other hand, the EU has recently pledged to evolve towards an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 [2]. Hence, reducing the energy demand deriving from fossil fuels in the European building sector appears as a pivotal challenge. In this context, near-zero Energy Buildings (nZEBs) are emerging as a new building paradigm. nZEBs are defined as buildings with very high energy performance. According to the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, nZEBs should require a low amount of primary energy and this should be mostly covered by renewable sources produced on-site or nearby. However, the identification of precise numerical indicators to classify new buildings as nZEBs is left to each Member State [3]. For instance, in Italy this definition is mainly related to the design of new buildings. As a matter of fact, the Italian legislation poses some threshold values both for the thermophysical characteristics of the building envelope and for the overall efficiency of its heating and cooling systems. However, the energy usage related to occupants' behaviour also constitutes an important part of the total energy use in buildings. Hence, as suggested by [4], the user related energy consumption should be included in the definition of nZEBs and such a consideration is applied in this work.

Anyway, innovating the built environment in Europe is expected to foster future substantial opportunities and social benefits, as pointed out by Santamouris in [5]. This renovation is a multifaceted problem, where solutions must be energy and cost efficient. For example, Pikas et al. [6] focused on the design of office building facades in the cold Estonian climate evaluating both technical feasibility and cost optimality. The authors also underlined how the use of photovoltaic panels was essential to achieve the nZEB condition. Similarly, Hamdy et al. [7] stated that the design of cost-optimal nZEBs requires exploring a large number of possible

combinations of energy-saving measures and energy-supply systems (such as renewable energy sources). In their study they proposed a simulation-based optimization method for these explorations applied to a single-family house in Finland. A further design method was proposed by Kim et al. [8], who developed a data mining approach based on large datasets of building information models. Case studies revealed that this design process supports project teams in discovering useful patterns to improve the energy efficiency of buildings during their design phase.

Nevertheless, despite the establishment of a policy framework and several design guidelines, a certain technological push is also required to increase the efficiency of the European building stock. In particular, two main challenges can be identified. On the one hand, the on-site energy generation from multiple renewable energy sources (RES) must be properly coordinated to match the building energy demand. On the other hand, there is a need to develop renewable energy technologies that can be better integrated in the urban fabric. Hence, this paper reflects on the solution envisioned by the EU project RE-cognition. This consists of an ICT integration framework developed on top of established and ad-hoc designed renewable energy technologies. Such an integration framework is tested and deployed in a real building located in Turin (Italy), known as Energy Center.

2. Methodology

The RE-cognition project aims at developing a technology-proof integration solution, which is tested in several pilot sites. Among these, the building owned by Politecnico di Torino known as Energy Center has a great potential for becoming a nZEB through the implementation of the project solution. This consists of an integration framework able to incorporate and manage existing energy technologies along with newly-developed RES and storage components. The core of the proposed integrated solution is an agent-based distributed intelligence. A general overview of the envisioned solution is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of RE-cognition integrated solution

2.1 RE-cognition ICT frameworks

The ICT infrastructure conceived in the RE-cognition project is composed of two key elements. These are a gateway able to dialogue with on-field assets and an agent-based distributed intelligence. The latter is called Automated Cognitive Energy Management Engine (ACEME) and constitutes the backbone of the proposed integrated solution. ACEME determines the optimal operation of the available energy technologies thanks to the several agents composing its structure and the flow of information exchanged with the gateway. As a result, ACEME proposes a day ahead optimised schedule that minimizes the daily operational cost, which is expressed as the sum of the energy costs produced by each asset.

ACEME's agents can operate autonomously, provided that they receive decision rules from a centralized control mechanism. These rules derive from forecasted data and simulations of the building energy flows. More

specifically, ACEME receives measurements from the on-site sensors and predicts patterns for the aggregated load of the building. Moreover, through the acquisition of weather information from local station units or online weather services, ACEME is able to predict RES generation within various time intervals. The most general version of this computational engine is composed of the following agents:

- The optimal dispatch agent, which determines the day-ahead schedule of the available energy resources;
- The centralized balancing agent, which translates the strategy selected by the optimal planning into actions that can be executed by on-field devices in a close to real-time scale;
- The auxiliary services agent, which is responsible for data retrieval from external services (e.g. energy prices or meteorological data);
- The forecasting agent, which predicts the future building energy demand and the RES generation profiles through machine learning algorithms;
- The asset agents, which are a virtual representation of the energy technologies deployed on-site and are responsible for the exchange of information with the gateway.

In addition, all the generated information (models, raw data, control actions, etc.) are stored in a common repository. As a result, both static (e.g. building characteristics) as well as dynamic information can be accessed by ACEME's agents through this database. An overview of this ICT framework is presented in Figure 2. It should be noticed that this figure depicts the most general configuration of the proposed ICT framework. Some of the listed agents and relative technologies will not be available at the Turin Energy Center (such as the battery storage and the EV charger).

Figure 2. Overview of RE-cognition ICT framework

2.2 RE-cognition technologies

A secondary outcome of the RE-cognition project is the development of various innovative renewable energy and storage technologies which are currently characterized by a mid-low Technology Readiness Level. These are:

- A micro combined heat and power (micro-CHP) running with biogas
- A vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) with variable geometry
- Building Integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV) panels
- A Latent Heat Thermal Storage (LHTS)
- A Hybrid Solar Cooling (HSC) unit

The micro-CHP provides 3.2 kW of electrical power and 15.6 kW of thermal power at full load. An ad-hoc design allows the gas turbine to maintain a stable combustion even when low-caloric gases (such as biogas) are burnt. The VAWT prototype displays an optimised design for good performance also at low wind speeds (nominal power: 1.2 kW). The BIPV panels developed in this project display two essential characteristics for their integration in buildings facades: they are light-weight and coloured. The LHTS allows to store thermal energy in the form of latent heat of an organic Phase Change Material (PCM). This device appears as a heat exchanger with 96 finned pipes immersed in the PCM. Its overall storage capacity reaches 40 kWh. Finally, the HSC unit prototype supports traditional cooling systems based on chillers through a solar dehumidification

process. This technology relies on the sorption properties of some micro porous materials (such as silica) which can absorb the vapour content in the process air until they are saturated. As a result, the coupled traditional chiller can operate at a higher supply temperature (implying better efficiency), since the dehumidification of the process air is no longer based on vapour condensation at atmospheric pressure. The adsorption material is then cyclically regenerated by low-temperature heat provided by solar thermal collectors.

2.3 RE-cognition case study: the Turin Energy Center

The Energy Center is a building owned and managed by Politecnico di Torino which hosts firms, academic staff and public administration who jointly develop research activities. This facility is developed on four floors with a total net surface of 5441 m². The Energy Center is equipped with several technologies for the satisfaction of the building energy demand. These are:

- Monocrystalline photovoltaic (PV) panels both on the rooftop and on the hall glass façade
- A ground-source heat pump (GSHP) that provides both heating and cooling (even simultaneously)
- Two District Heating (DH) substations for space heating and domestic hot water (DHW) production

The existing grid-connected PV system is distributed in different zones of the building, as shown in Figure 3. There are two free-standing plants on the rooftop and a series of PV cells integrated in the hall façade. The total gross surface is 261 m² with a nominal overall capacity of 47 kW. The GSHP, located in the basement, is an open-loop groundwater heat pump. This machine uses R134a as working fluid and it is able to supply at the same time heat and cooling thanks to two independent circuits. The GSHP is mainly used for cooling during summer and for supporting the production of domestic hot water. Indeed, this type of heat pump has a recovery mode allowing to produce heat for DHW during the cooling season. During winter, instead, the heating demand of the building is supplied by the local district heating provider. The nominal capacity of this substation is 350 kW.

Figure 3. Aerial view of the Energy Center building

A widespread net of sensors allows to monitor the most relevant physical quantities necessary to manage and control the energy assets of the building. Hence, the agent-based distributed intelligence (ACEME) developed in this project can be easily added as a further virtual control layer.

Alongside these existing assets, some of the energy technologies specifically developed in the RE-cognition project are being installed in the building premises. These are the micro-CHP (Figure 4a), the LHTS (Figure 4b) and the HSC. However, due to the difficulty of finding a continuous biogas supply in such an urban context during the project timeframe, it was decided to feed the micro-CHP with the natural gas available from the local grid. If the micro-CHP proves good performance for this pilot site, a biogas feed will be considered. Unfortunately, it was not possible to install the remaining newly-developed RE-cognition technologies (VAWT and BIPV). Two lab-scale wind turbines already present on the facility rooftop showed that the local wind conditions are not favourable. On the other hand, legal restrictions on the building façade did not allow to install the lightweight and coloured BIPV in the project framework. Nevertheless, the existing PV panels integrated in the hall windows offer a good example of how this technology might respond in the present context.

Figure 4. micro-CHP (a) and LHTS (b) units at the Turin Energy Center

3. Results and discussion

To demonstrate the potential of integrating different renewable energy technologies orchestrated by an intelligent automated algorithm, three cases are here presented based on the available building monitored data. First, the actual facility energy demand and local production is evaluated in a reference day. This represents a benchmark for the successive cases. The same evaluation is thus repeated with the ideal addition of the installed RE-cognition prototypes. Finally, the impact of an upscaled version of the renewable technologies is also assessed. With the aim of highlighting the different performance between the summer and winter seasons, two representative days are selected among those monitored in 2021 (one in June and the other in December). The choice of displaying the results for a single day instead of the whole season is due to the fact that ACEME proposes a day ahead optimisation schedule. As already anticipated, the main goal implemented in the algorithm is to minimize the daily operational cost, expressed as the sum of the energy costs produced by each asset.

3.1 Case 0: energy performance with current technologies

The daily electricity demand and production in the selected representative summer day is shown in Figure 5. The overall electricity demand is largely affected by the operation of the GSHP in cooling mode. This represents almost 40% of the total. The remainder is attributable to the large number of appliances and the devices belonging to the offices and the building centralised systems. Indeed, a significant amount of stand-by energy consumption is visible even when the facility is closed (between 22.00 pm and 7.00 am). On the contrary, the contribution of the existing PV system appears to be marginal even in sunny days. As a matter of fact, also the electricity produced throughout the year is entirely consumed locally and the total PV share is lower than 10%.

During the winter season, the daily electricity consumption is lower compared to summer days. The energy consumption due to stand-by is approximately the same, however a higher electricity demand due to lighting appliances is evident in the middle of the day (Figure 6). Nevertheless, throughout the heating season (from 15th October to 15th April) the GSHP is turned off in favour of the DH supply, hence the peak electricity demand is drastically reduced (-25% with respect to summer). The DH substation is generally switched on between 6.00 am and 22.00 pm, while it is idle during the night. As a result, a noticeable peak energy demand is often experienced at the start.

Figure 5. Daily electricity demand in summer (case 0)

Figure 6. Daily electricity demand in winter (case 0)

3.2 Case 1: energy performance with RE-cognition prototypal technologies

This section analyses the impact that some of the renewable energy technologies developed in the project might have on the same summer and winter reference days. Although the size of these prototypal technologies is small by definition compared to the energy demand in the pilot site, it is important to reflect on their effect in view of the project conclusion. As previously mentioned, the additional RE-cognition technologies considered in this case are the micro-CHP, the Hybrid Solar Cooling (HSC) and the Latent Heat Thermal Storage (LHTS). The micro-CHP is operated both in summer (mainly useful for electricity production) and winter (both for electricity and heat). On the contrary, the HSC is available in summer, while the LHTS is mostly needed in winter.

As shown in Figure 7, the micro-CHP would ideally produce a baseload that sums up to the electricity generated by the existing PV system in both seasons. At the same time, the presence of the HSC in summer would slightly reduce the electricity consumption for cooling purposes (-3% with respect to case 0), although this is not appreciable in the graph as the GSHP would still be largely employed (Figure 7a). As expected, the proposed prototypal size of the HSC is rather small for the Energy Center cooling demand. Overall, the daily electricity withdrawn from the grid would be reduced by roughly 6% with respect to case 0 in both seasons

mainly thanks to the deployment of the m-CHP. As a result, this would still imply an appreciable cost reduction over the facility electricity bill.

Figure 7. a) Daily electricity demand in summer (case 1); b) Daily electricity demand in winter (case 1)

The heat generated by the micro-CHP is suitable for coupling with the LHTS, especially in winter when space heating is required. As depicted in Figure 8, these two technologies combined together would determine a slight reduction in the energy requested to the local DH network. More specifically, the LHTS would be charged by the micro-CHP a few hours before the DH morning start and discharged during the peak energy demand. This would decrease the instant peak energy request by more than 10% with respect to case 0, thus generating a positive feedback for the local DH provider and, consequently, an economic advantage.

Figure 8. Daily heat demand in winter (case 1)

3.3 Case 2: energy performance with RE-cognition upscaled technologies

Following the results presented in the previous section, the potential impact of upscaled renewable energy technologies is here evaluated. It is estimated that the existing PV system capacity could be increased by 5 times exploiting part of the surface that is still available on the building rooftop. Hence, the electricity production of the local PV system is ideally multiplied by this factor. Similarly, it is assumed that four additional micro-CHP units could be simultaneously managed on site. Hence, also the overall micro-CHP available capacity is multiplied by a factor 5. Then, considering the good pairing between the micro-CHP and the LHTS, also the thermal storage size is increased 5 times. Finally, the HSC technology has a great upscaling potential. It is estimated that the prototypal version requires around 13 m² of solar collectors for the silica regeneration phase. Hence, considering the rooftop surface that remains available after increasing the number of PV panels and the ground surface with good solar exposure, it is estimated that the HSC could be confidently upscaled by a factor 10 without interfering with the other technologies.

Figure 9. Daily electricity demand in summer (case 2)

As a result, the ideal electricity consumption and production daily profiles are presented in Figure 9 (for summer) and Figure 10 (for winter). The micro-CHP would still be suitable for an electricity baseload during most of the day. However, during the central hours of the day, its power production should be curtailed in favour of the photovoltaic production (especially in summer). With the aforementioned hypotheses, it is estimated that almost 7% of the PV electricity production exceeds the electricity demand. This amount of energy could be further locally reused if a suitable pack of batteries were installed. Furthermore, the HSC capacity increment effectively reduces the electricity consumption for cooling (-35% with respect to case 0). This is due to the fact that most of the latent heat load is removed by the pack of silica, thus the heat pump working in cooling mode is more efficient.

Figure 10. Daily electricity demand in winter (case 2)

When considering a typical winter day, the heat produced by the micro-CHP is employed in the same way as case 1. However, due to the electricity curtailment in the central hours of the day, it is more convenient to discharge the LHTS in those hours to compensate the lower heat production of the micro-CHP (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Daily heat demand in winter (case 2)

3.4 Evaluation of Key Performance Indicators

The presented case studies are here analysed in light of different Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These cover the three main fields of interest for this project: energy, environmental and economic. Concerning the pilot site energy performance, the selected KPIs are self-consumption and self-sufficiency. The former quantifies how much local energy production is consumed on-site, while the latter expresses the relevance of the local energy production over the total building demand. Regarding the environmental performance, the elected KPI is the amount of CO₂ emissions. This is obtained through the emission factors of the Italian electrical grid (276 gCO₂/kWh, from [9]) and the local DH network (161 gCO₂/kWh, from [10]). Finally, the economic performance is evaluated in terms of daily operating energy cost, which coincides with the objective function of ACEME's algorithm.

Table 1 and Table 2 summarise the results respectively for the reference summer day and winter day.

Table 1. KPIs for a typical summer day

KPI	<i>Case 0</i>	<i>Case 1</i>	<i>Case 2</i>
RES self-consumption [-]	100%	100%	96%
Self-sufficiency [-]	10%	14%	72%
CO ₂ emissions [kg/day]	478	450	131
Normalized operating cost [-]	1	0.94	0.27

Table 2. KPIs for a typical winter day

KPI	<i>Case 0</i>	<i>Case 1</i>	<i>Case 2</i>
Electricity: RES self-consumption [-]	100%	100%	96%
Electricity: Self-sufficiency [-]	6%	11%	52%
Heat: RES self-consumption [-]	-	100%	100%
Heat: Self-sufficiency [-]	-	8%	35%
CO ₂ emissions [kg/day]	918	871	639
Normalized operating cost [-]	1	0.95	0.70

As expected, the size of the prototypal technologies cannot provide a significant contribution to the building self-sufficiency. However, the hypothetical scaled versions (*case 2*) appear to be beneficial from an energy, environmental and economic perspective. Nevertheless, the KPIs on CO₂ emissions and self-sufficiency indirectly show that it would still be difficult to strongly reduce the dependency on fossil fuels with this set of technologies. Thus, when considering the user related energy consumption, this building can hardly be classified as nZEB and further improvements should be considered. Moreover, it should be remarked that a constant biogas supply might be hard to obtain in an urban context, although this aspect is not considered in this study.

4. Conclusions

This paper discusses the current and future potential achievements of the integrated technological solution envisioned by the European project RE-cognition. This is applied to the real case study represented by the Turin Energy Center. This pilot site has the potential for becoming a paradigm for near-Zero Energy Buildings if the outcomes of the RE-cognition project are further developed. Indeed, this project aims at validating the integration between an ad-hoc developed ICT framework and innovative RETs for energy efficient buildings. Thanks to its already existing multi-energy sources, available spaces and energy consumption data, the Energy Center is suitable for testing the RE-cognition integrated solution towards nZEBs. The newly-developed prototypes of a micro-CHP, HSC and LHTS are currently being installed at this pilot site along with the existing PV system, DH and GSHP. Hence, this study provides insights on how their integration and hypothetical upscale could facilitate the transition of the Energy Center towards a more efficient building. Nevertheless, results show that the condition of near-Zero Energy Building is difficult to reach when considering the user related energy consumption in this definition. As a matter of fact, further improvements should be implemented to achieve such a condition. For instance, these might be the addition of electrical storage batteries and the further extension of the PV system through the inclusion of BIPV panels on the building opaque facades. These solutions would largely reduce the Energy Center primary energy consumption and maximize the building independence from external non-renewable energy sources.

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